

ARASF

Atmospheric Research Airborne Support Facility

Flight Data Catalogue

Flight

A574

13 September 1997

ACSOE

Instrument Test and Model Validation

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. A 574

DATE: 13/9/97

Take off: 1750 Z

Landing: 2230

Aircraft Scientist : H. RICHEN
Flight Leader : I. POLE
Others CO. : S. SCHWARTZ
NO. 4 : S. BARRIETTE
MEMORIDE : B. DAVOY
FOURMONTIDE : G. WILLS
GEEC : J. KENT
MANCA : T. GIBSON
+ A. KATE
K. DAVOY
D. BARRIETTE

Captain : M. PURSE
Co-pilot : C. O'BRYEN
Navigator : T. SIMPSON
Engineer : K. QUICK
Loadmaster : M. LEWIS

GRAND CREW : J. VINGWOOD, S. ASHLEY, P. STERLING

Trials Instructions MAP1 AREA/PCOE :

Operating area : BOGUMBA DOWN TO ST MANUA

General synoptic situation

TIME :

A574, 13th September, 1997
ACSOE
Transit Boscombe Down to Santa Maria

<u>Start time</u>	<u>End time</u>	<u>Event</u>	<u>Height(s)</u>	<u>Hdg</u>	<u>Comments</u>
175015					Take off Boscombe Down
175711	180911	P1	3000' FL180	260°	
180911	220657	R1	FL180	255°	
220657	222156	P2	FL180 3500'		
223112					Land St Maria

Debrief

The aircraft availability, to the scientific crew, was delayed due to the length of time required for instrument tests. Therefore, both the instrument warm up time and the take-off time were delayed. We departed Boscombe Down at 18:50 local. Hence, most of the flight was in near darkness. The NO_x instrument, in particular, was effected by the short warm up time. The NO_y background decreased markedly, during the first hour of flight, to give reasonable readings towards the latter half of the flight. The NO background remained somewhat variable, even towards the end of flight, but in order to correct for this the instrument was frequently zeroed. The PAN instrument was not operated but set at high temperature in order to clean the ECD's. The formaldehyde measurements were not seen by the scientists as they were above the maximum displayed on HORACE. The high background was thought, by the instrument operator, to be due to contaminated solutions. The peroxide instrument appeared to work well but it was near the detection limit of the instrument for much of the flight, as forecast by the Bergen chemical model: on nearing Santa Maria peroxide values increased to 0.6, again as expected by model output. Ozone and CO concentrations were lowest on leaving the UK. There was no evidence of the associated high ozone levels from the low pressure system which had moved to the East of the UK. There was little structure in the ozone and CO levels on the transit to Santa Maria with maximum concentrations of the two species reaching 60 and 80 ppb respectively.

A total of 9 bottles were filled, at half-hourly intervals during the transit, for subsequent hydrocarbon analysis.

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be 'H. R.', followed by a long horizontal line extending to the right.

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: HANNAH RICHER

Project: AC50E
Flight No: A574

Date: 13/9/97
Page 1 of 3

Time GMT	Run Profile	Height	Heading INS	Latitude	Other Information (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
				Longitude	
17554		3000 <small>Pres Rad FL</small>	257	51.03 -2.24	INSTRUMENT TESTS Hdd 3000ft for
175711	PROBLE ①				CLOUD ABOVE START OF PROFILE 1
		3000 8000 <small>Pres Rad FL</small>			INVERSION 800 ML 8000ft - DRY SLOT ALSO 7500ML CONDITIONALLY UNSTABLE UP TO THIS POINT
					PROFILE TO FL170 - REQUIREMENT TO SAVE FUEL!
180224		FL170 <small>Pres Rad FL</small>			VERY SLIGHT INVERSION
180411	Run 1				START OF RUN / END OF PROFILE NO BOTTLES FILLED UNTIL WE HAVE DOXY CONFIRMATION
180418					
181818	Run 1	1800 <small>Pres Rad FL</small>	256		SMALL CU BELOW 6/8 OVER LAND (CORNWALL) CIRCUS THIN
					OZONE / CO CORRELATIONS OZONE ca 45 CO ca. 75
182315		180 <small>Pres Rad FL</small>		50.34 -4.87	(COMPAR ca. 79 O ₃ ca 49)
182850				50.15 -5.96	CO CAL

AIRCRAFT SCIENTIST'S LOG

Aircraft Scientist: HANNAH RICHER

Project: ACSOE
Flight No: A574

Date: 31/9/97
Page 2 of 3

Time GMT	Run Profile	Height	Heading INS	Latitude Longitude	Other Information (eg: clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
		Pres Rad FL			O ₃ Max increasing to ca. 55 ppb NO HIGH O ₃ OBSERVED AT ALL
184115	R1	180	244	49.67 -6.73	BOTTLE FILL REQUESTED (AS CO REACHED AT MAX OF 83 PPB)
		Pres Rad FL			FILLED AT 1845 (20 secs)
		Pres Rad FL			BOTTLE FILLED AT 1915 REQUESTED
191500	H	180	229	47.89 -10.39	BOTTLE FILLED
191000 219200	R1	"	"		CO / O ₃ anti correlation?
		Pres Rad FL			PEROXIDE MODEL IS VERY OUT
194500		Pres Rad FL		45.82 -12.96	BOTTLE FILL REQUESTED
191804		Pres Rad FL			O ₂ one dropped from 50 → 35 ppb
		Pres Rad FL			
		Pres Rad FL			

Interactive Processing Log

Flight No. A574 Date: 15/9/97 User: H. RICHER
Interactive by: I. RUS
Date: 20/9/97

Renav

KALMAN FILTERING USED

TWC

NOT FITTED

Profile plotted :

Line chosen : Profile / Whole flight / Other

a = -

b = +

c = +

LWC

Heimann / Barnes

NOT USED

POST FLIGHT REQUIREMENTS FORM

Flight No: AS74

Date: 13/9/97

A/S Name: H. RICHER

Aircraft Scientist's Post Flight Requirements:

1. Are any copies of the flight folder required?
YES NO for SEPARATE FOLDER NERC
2. Flight data and folders will normally be discarded after 10 years, is this OK?
YES NO If not OK, state period INDEF
3. Is the flight part of an international project or major campaign?
YES NO Name of Project AT. SOE
4. Do you want the video tape kept?
YES NO How long? NOT USED
5. Has the Handheld camera or the Camcorder been used:
YES NO
If yes, do you want the handheld camera film processed:
immediately or when the film is finished?
6. Do you want the cloud physics data kept?
YES NO
If yes, which disc / file do you want it stored in? NOT USED
7. Do you want to do the interactive processing?
YES NO

NOTE:

- Members of MRF Radiation and Cloud Physics groups are expected to meet their own requirements for data storage and non-standard processing.
- For non MRF users, Data Management Section will keep the processed data TEMPORARILY until the requirements are made known.
- Any other requirements for post-flight processing and data storage should be discussed with the Data Management Section.
- If copies of the Flight Folder are required, it is the responsibility of the Aircraft Scientist / User to produce them.

Flight Leader's Pre/In-Flight Check List

Flight No: A574

Date: 13/9/97

Page...of 1

CHEK for auto selection

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	REF +	5	0567	✓		Approx	0568
	REF -	7	2853	✓		Approx	2858
	AOSS	19	1949	F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	AOA	18	1847	F/S O/S	TORQUE	2047 st. and level	
	RD HT	37	4045		18000'	As Indicated	0000
	PR HT	8	1957	18000'	✓ 18000'	As Altimeter	
	CABP	14	3188	270	✓		
	A/S	9	2244	230	232 ✓	As ASI	0000 - 0100
	UP1S	81	0000				
	UP2S	82	0110				
	UIRS	83	0028				
	UP1Z	84	0280			Approx	0147
	UP2Z	85	0140	✓		Approx	0149 <i>RED DANCE</i>
	UIRZ	86	0027			Approx 2061	
	UP1T	87	0282			As IAT	
	UP2T	88	2052			As IAT	
	UIRT	89	0000			As IAT	
	LP1S	91	0200				
	LP2S	92	0127				
	LIRS	93	0212				
	LP1Z	94	0000			Approx	0150
	LP2Z	95	0152	✓		Approx	0146 <i>RED DANCE</i>
	LIRZ	96	0211			Approx 2050	
	LP1T	97	0200			As IAT	
	LP2T	98	2076			As IAT	
	LIRT	99	0200			As IAT	
	J/W	42	1033	0000	0	As Indicated	0000
	HYGR	58	1758	-24			
	HYCC	59	0750	✓		696-901	
	FDEW	138	1480	✓		DP = (DRSU/20)-100 C	
	FSTA	139	0092				
	DTF	10	2737	-6			
	DTC	11	4				
	NDTF	23	2497	-6		same as De-Iced	
	NDTC	24	4				
	INCT	48	2036	✓			
	HEIM	141	2279	✓			
	PRTC	142	1904	CAL		approx	2380
	TWCD	70	4045			0000-4094	
	TSAM	72	4045	NOT FITTED		0640-1860 < min	
	O3	100	0177	} ✓			
	O3P	106	1963				
	O3RG	113	1860				

Flight Leaders' Pre/In-Flight Check List

BCDS for auto selection

GMT	PARA.	NO.	H/D	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTR	EXPECTED VALUE
	FL NO	1	Hex	574	✓		Flight No.
	GMTH	2	Hex	0183	✓		Clock: First 4 No.s
	GMTM	3	Hex	0838	✓		Clock: Last 4 No.s
	E/M	4	Hex	4	✓		Event Mark Counter
	INCH	49	Dec				Multipxd Hkeeping
227A	3855	1287	1487	2285	3784	2275	0173
	1260	1287	1487				
	LATC	160	Dec	0565	50		Latitude
	LONC	161	Dec	4020	~6		Longitude

Total Water Content Meter Check List

TOTW for auto selection **NOT FITTED** Height:

GMT	PARA	NO	D.R.S.	DECODE	INSTRUMENT	EXPECTED VALUES	
						INFLIGHT	PREFLIGHT
	TWCD	70				0001-4095	
	TNOS	71				2000-3460	< min
	TSAM	72				0640-1860	< min
	TAMB	73				2400-3200	
	TSRC	74				2160-2470	
	HTR1	75				0000-4095	< 4095
	HTR2	76				0000-4095	< 4095
	ISRC	77				0001-1230	< min
	STAT	78				4095	
	EV1V	170					
	EV2V	171					
	NPWR	172					
	EVIC	173					
	EV2C	174					

BROAD BAND RADIOMETER FIT

(pre-Flight only)

	PARA NO	POSITION	DOMES	COVERS	OBSCURERS
UPPER	81,84,87	Port	Clear 301D	Off/ On	Large/Small
	82,85,88	Stbd	Red		
	83,86,89	Centre	Silicon 301D		
LOWER	91,94,97	Port	Clear 301D	Off/ On	
	92,95,98	Stbd	Red		
	93,96,99	Centre	Silicon 301D		

Flight Leader's In-Flight Log

Flight No A 574.....

Date 13/9/97.....

Page 1..... of 1.....

Video Tape	
No.	
Ends	NIL
FFC / DFC / RFC	

	GPS	INU
Lat	51 09.87 N	51 09.83 N
Long	001 44.61 W	001 44.65 W
Time	1711	1713
Status	53	GC ALIGN

DRS recording to HORACE	☒ y / n
HORACE recording to disc	☒ y / n
SATCOM sending pos. reports	☒ y / n

GMT	EVM	Height	QNH	Hdg	IAS	TAT	DP	DI Htr	Wind/ Sea st.
165024			DATA ON						
172650			SET INU TO NAV						
175015			T/O						
			START P1						
175711	2	3000		260					
			END P1 / START RUN 1						
180411	3	FL180		255					
			END RUN 1 / START PROFILE 2						
220657	5	FL180							
				END P2					
222156	6	3800	(020)						
23112				LAND ST MARHA					
223504				DATA OFF					
								GPS POSITION	
								36 58.98 N	
								25 09.95 W	

SAMPLE BOTTLE RECORD

G.C. Form 3

light No. A574

Date 13/9/97

Sheet no. 1/1

Bottle no.	Time	E/M	Height	PRESSURE			True pressure (mb)	Remarks (Run no. etc.)
				PURGE TIME	FILL TIME	END TIME		
N 309	184500		FL 180	184200	184500	184520	589	TRANSIT 49.45N 7.24W APL TO C.2.8 Bar
N 202	191500		FL 180	191200	191500	191520	588	TRANSIT 47.91N 10.07W
N 319	194800		FL 180	194400	194800	194822	588	TRANSIT 45.97N 12.78
N 331	201500		FL 180	200800	201500	201525	588	LONGER FLUSH. TRANSIT 44.41N 14.92W
N 317	204500		FL 180	204200	204800	204525	588	TRANSIT 42.78 17.43
N 303	211500		FL 180	211200	211500	211525	589	TRANSIT 41.04 19.91W
N 307	214500		FL 180	214200	214500	214525	589	TRANSIT 39.23N 22.20W
N 320	214500		FL 180	215900	220700	220715	588	TRANSIT TO D JUST INTO START OF PROFILE 37.89N 23.77W
N 313			3500	222200	222300	222355	988	BOTTOM OF PROFILE

FLIGHT LEADER'S INSTRUMENT STATUS REPORT

FLIGHT NO: A574

DATE: 13 / 9 / 97

MRF | ACSO:

INSTRUMENT	FITTED	OPERATED	COMMENTS
NAVIGATION:			
GPS	✓	✓	
OMEGA	✓	✓	
INU	✓	✓	
RADALT	✓	✓	
THERMOMETERS:			
DI TEMP	✓	✓	
NDI TEMP	✓	✓	
ICTP	✓	✓	
HEIMANN	✓	✓	
HYGROMETERS:			
GEN. EASTERN	✓	✓	
TWC	X		
FWVS	✓	✓	
J/W	✓	✓	
EXP. PITOT HEAD:			
STATIC PRESS.	✓	✓	
PITOT PRESS.	✓	✓	
GUST VANES	✓	✓	
RADIOMETERS:			
UPPER CLEAR	NO JOD ✓	✓	
UPPER RED	✓	✓	
UPPER SILICON	JNO ✓	✓	
LOWER CLEAR	JOD ✓	✓	
LOWER RED	✓	✓	
LOWER SILICON	JNO ✓	✓	
MARSS	X		
SAFIRE	X		
DEIMOS	X		
ARIES	X		
CHEMISTRY:			
OZONE	✓	✓	
ECGC	✓	✓	
NOX	✓	✓	
OTHERS:			
CCN	✓	X	
CLOUD PHYSICS	X		
CABIN PRESS	✓	✓	
NEPHELOMETER	X		
PSAP	✓	✓	

LIST OF FORMS USED ON FLIGHT

No. of forms	Form Title
✓	Aircraft Scientist de-briefing sheet Aircraft Scientist log Aircraft Scientist post flight requirements sheet Interactive log
✓	Flight Leader pre-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight check form Flight Leader in-flight log Flight Leader Video tape log (photocopy original)
✓	SAFIRE log CCN log MARSS log DEIMOS log Chemistry log <i>BOTTLE LOG</i>
	Particulate / Filter boom Operator's log 2DC / FSSP / Holography Operator's log Sonde Ejector's log Navigator's log Photographic log (photocopy original)
✓ ✓ ✓ ✓ ✓	Instrument status forms RTD prints Raw data plots Weather charts Satellite pictures GPS track

A574 13-SEP-97 Data starts 16:50:34 Data ends 22:35:06

Header file EAGLE\$DUA0:[RAWDATA]A574_RAW_HDDR.DAT;

Data file EAGLE\$DUA0:[RAWDATA]A574_RAW_DATA.DAT; 40.4 Mbytes (82680 blocks)

Transcription on 24-SEP-97 12:20:45

Extraction on 24-SEP-97 12:20:45

Data set type 2

ISS 31 DBF 31 IC 02 121 parameters recorded 889 samples per second

2 sections of data

Section	Starts					Ends				
	GMT	SEC	EVM	BLK	REC	GMT	SEC	EVM	BLK	REC
1	16:50:34	060634	000	00010	00001	17:11:55	061915	001	01291	01282
2	17:11:59	061919	001	01295	01283	22:35:06	081306	006	20682	20670

ASXX EGRR MSLP ANALYSIS DT 0000 UTC 13 SEP 1997

Polar Stereographic Projection, Standard Parallel 60°N, Original scale 1:20m

Revised and drawn in the Geographic Service, MET-OFFICE, Brundage, MET-OFFICE DT 0000 UTC 13 SEP 1997

FSXX EGRR 24H MSLP FORECAST VT 1200 UTC 13 SEP 1997

Polar Stereographic Projection, Standard Parallels 60°N, Original scale 1:20m

Prepared and drawn by the Cartographic Service, Met Office, Exeter, Devon, England. MSLP (Sea Level Pressure) Forecast. 13 SEP 1997.

Polar Stereographic Projection, Standard Parallel 60°N, Original scale 1:20M

Prepared and drawn to the Geographic Service, National Defense Science and Engineering Graduate School, Arlington, Virginia, August 1959. Approved July 1959.

13 SEP '97 15:39

** TOTAL PAGE .001 **
MET_OFFICE_ARTIFAX_6 PAGE .001

11 00Z SAT 15/ 9/97

01 00Z SUN 14/ 9/97

GMTAIN T + 24

HEIGHT DM.

300MB

POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 05.43.40

CHART 27

PHDE30 EGRR 0000Z

13 SEP '97 07:40

MET-OFFICE-ARTIFAX-5 PAGE.001

CHART 27 PHDE50 EGRR 0000Z

GLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03.13.57

PHDA30 EGRR 0000Z

CHART 27

13 SEP 97 07:43

MET OFFICE ARTIFAX-5 PAGE. 003

300MB

HEIGHT DM.

0

GMAIN

13/ 9/97

VI UUZ SHI

15/ 9/97

YEAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03.34.28

THICKNESS DM.
HEIGHT DM.

I + 0

GMAIN

13/ 9/97

VI 00Z SAI

13/ 9/97

VI 00Z SAI

PHDA50 EGRR 0000Z

CHART 27

POLAR STEREOGRAPHIC PROJECTION AT 60N SCALE 1:20M RUN TIME 03.34.14

NOW PROBABILITY AT MSL
TOTAL PPN RATE
PRESSURE AT MSL

DI 12Z SATURDAY 13/9/1997 L MAIN

SNOW CONVECTIVE
DYNAM: C
-03 .1 .5 1.0 MM/HR AT VI

..1 10 .5 N=10 O=11 C=12 O=13 E=14 F=15 O=16 N=17 J=18 N=19 L=20 M=21 N=22 P=23 O=24 N=25-29 S=30-34 T=35-39 U=40-44 V=45-49 W=50-54 X=55-59 Y=60-64 Z=65 AND OVER

MM/HR AT VT

SNOW
CONVECTIVE
DYNAMIC

DT 00Z SATURDAY 13/9/1997 LMAIN

MM PROBABILITY AT MSL

MM PPN RATE

MM SSURE AT MSL

T+12 VI 12Z SATURDAY 13/9/1997

NOW PROBABILITY AT MSL
TOTAL PPN RATE
PRESSURE AT MSL

DT 00Z SATURDAY 13/9/1997 LMAIN

SNOW CONVECTIVE DYNAMIC
.03 .1 .5 1.0 MM/HR AT VT

T+24 VT 0Z SUNDAY 14/9/1997

STATION: 08509
 LAJES (ACORES)
 TIME: 130000 +12 SEP 97

mb	Deg	Kts
MAX WINDS: NIL		
150	355	33
201	305	23
252	330	17
303	325	9
359	290	9
428	260	16
512	255	14
610	235	12
713	215	12
807	190	13
897	175	12
948	165	13
994	150	13
1015	150	12

Parts : A C D missing

STATION: 08509	
LAJES (ACRES)	
TIME: 130000 +24 SEP 97	
mb	Deg Kts
MAX WINDS: NIL	
150	300
201	295
251	260
302	290
358	300
427	270
511	230
609	225
711	235
806	225
885	200
946	180
992	170
1014	165
Parts : A C D missing	

99317

WORLD AREA FORECAST CENTRE
LONDON

UPPER WIND AND TEMPERATURE

CHART FOR FL 050

VALID 12 UTC 13 SEP 97

TEMPERATURES ARE NEGATIVE
UNLESS PREFIXED BY 'PS'
DATA TIME 12 UTC 12 SEP 97

FCRR 12007

99316

WORLD AREA FORECAST CENTRE
LONDON

UPPER WIND AND TEMPERATURE

CHART FOR FL 100

VALID 12 UTC 13 SEP 97

TEMPERATURES ARE NEGATIVE
UNLESS PREFIXED BY 'PS'
DATA TIME 12 UTC 12 SEP 97

EGR 1200Z

99315

WORLD AREA FORECAST CENTRE
LONDON

UPPER WIND AND TEMPERATURE

CHART FOR FL 180

VALID 12 UTC 13 SEP 97

TEMPERATURES ARE NEGATIVE
UNLESS PREFIXED BY 'PS'
DATA TIME 12 UTC 12 SEP 97

1 FARR 17007

99314

WORLD AREA FORECAST CENTRE
LONDON

UPPER WIND AND TEMPERATURE

CHART FOR FL 240

VALID 12 UTC 13 SEP 97

TEMPERATURES ARE NEGATIVE
UNLESS PREFIXED BY 'PS'
DATA TIME 12 UTC 12 SEP 97

EGRR 1200Z

99313

WORLD AREA FORECAST CENTRE
LONDON

UPPER WIND AND TEMPERATURE

CHART FOR FL 300

VALID 12 UTC 13 SEP 97

TEMPERATURES ARE NEGATIVE
UNLESS PREFIXED BY 'PS'
DATA TIME 12 UTC 12 SEP 97

FCRR 12007

A574

From 0Z 10/ 9/1997 to 0Z 14/ 9/1997

Arrows every 24 hrs

Plotted 19-May-1998 08:36

A574 13-SEP-97

P1 3000' - FL180 (175711-180911) + P2 FL180 - 3500' (220657-222156)

A574 13-SEP-97 P1 3000' - FL180 From 175711-180911 Global 6-May-1998 08:48

A574 13-SEP-97 P1 3000' - FL180 From 175711-180911 Plotted 6-May-1998 08:48

10 11 12

A574 13-SEP-97 P1 3000' - FL180 From 175711-180911 Plotted 6-May-1998 08:48

A574 13-SEP-97 R1 FL180 From 180911-200000 Plotted 6-May-1998 14:03

A574 13-SEP-97 R1 FL180 From 180911-200000 Plotted 6-May-1998 14:03

A574 13-SEP-97 R1 FL180 From 180911-200000 Plotted 6-May-1998 14:04

A574 13-SEP-97 R1 FL180 From 180911-200000 Plotted 6-May-1998 14:04

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 6650
 Mean 507.027
 Standard dev 0.325051
 Max value 508.406
 Min value 505.258

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 6650
 Mean 256.842
 Standard dev 2.00762
 Max value 260.714
 Min value 253.630

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 6650
 Mean 244.492
 Standard dev 5.54496
 Max value 253.442
 Min value 231.528

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 6650
 Mean 48.9909
 Standard dev 5.82068
 Max value 60.8571
 Min value 32.2049

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()

No of obs 6650
 Mean 1.126226e-06
 Standard dev 3.969312e-06
 Max value 4.715912e-05
 Min value -1.046657e-09

JNO2 TOTAL (10-3/S)

No of obs 6650
 Mean 13.8800
 Standard dev 20.2661
 Max value 43.9000
 Min value 1.000000e-38

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 6650
 Mean 5471.30
 Standard dev 4.74078
 Max value 5497.13
 Min value 5451.22

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 6650
 Mean 48.3624
 Standard dev 1.62625
 Max value 50.7709
 Min value 45.2906

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 6650
 Mean -8.88580
 Standard dev 3.27921
 Max value -3.33330
 Min value -121.301

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 6650
 Mean -6.08501
 Standard dev 5.62491
 Max value 334.689
 Min value -14.8914

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 6650
 Mean 16.5685
 Standard dev 4.42483
 Max value 327.747
 Min value 3.70496

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 6650
 Mean 0.269391
 Standard dev 4.90515
 Max value 398.904
 Min value -13.3927

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 6648
 Mean 17.8593
 Standard dev 3.29654
 Max value 24.7953
 Min value 12.7176

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 290.166

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 6650
 Mean 158.780
 Standard dev 3.86726
 Max value 162.140
 Min value 127.108

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 231.273

A574 13-SEP-97 R1 (Continued) FL180 From 200001-210000 Plotted 6-May-1998 14:35

A574 13-SEP-97 R1 (Continued) FL180 From 200001-210000 Plotted 6-May-1998 14:35

A574 13-SEP-97 R1 (Continued) FL180 From 200001-210000 Plotted 6-May-1998 14:36

A574 13-SEP-97 R1 (Continued) FL180 From 200001-210000 Plotted 6-May-1998 14:36

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 3600
 Mean 506.818
 Standard dev 0.103399
 Max value 507.132
 Min value 506.556

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 3600
 Mean 262.307
 Standard dev 0.722750
 Max value 263.675
 Min value 260.671

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 3600
 Mean 240.350
 Standard dev 3.23696
 Max value 246.678
 Min value 232.387

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 3600
 Mean 41.1048
 Standard dev 4.10960
 Max value 55.2288
 Min value 32.9968

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()

No of obs 3600
 Mean 5.178298e-07
 Standard dev 8.948757e-07
 Max value 5.970294e-06
 Min value -1.046657e-09

JNO2 TOTAL (10-3/S)

No of obs 3600
 Mean 43.9000
 Standard dev 0.000000
 Max value 43.9000
 Min value 43.9000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 3600
 Mean 5474.35
 Standard dev 1.50772
 Max value 5478.17
 Min value 5469.77

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 3600
 Mean 43.6513
 Standard dev 0.950938
 Max value 45.2897
 Min value 41.9579

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 3600
 Mean -16.1337
 Standard dev 1.43920
 Max value -13.6353
 Min value -18.5929

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 3600
 Mean -2.96893
 Standard dev 0.563303
 Max value -2.07750
 Min value -4.19045

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 3600
 Mean 12.2412
 Standard dev 2.56857
 Max value 16.2608
 Min value 7.07957

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 3600
 Mean 0.220903
 Standard dev 0.175970
 Max value 0.738060
 Min value -0.280182

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 3600
 Mean 12.6374
 Standard dev 2.42297
 Max value 16.7006
 Min value 8.08831

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 283.633

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 3600
 Mean 158.922
 Standard dev 0.342263
 Max value 160.183
 Min value 158.145

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 227.203

A574 13-SEP-97 R1 (Continued) FL180 From 210001-220657 Plotted 6-May-1998 14:58

A574 13-SEP-97 R1 (Continued) FL180 From 210001-220657 Plotted 6-May-1998 14:58

A574 13-SEP-97 R1 (Continued) FL180 From 210001-220657 Plotted 6-May-1998 14:58

A574 13-SEP-97 R1 (Continued) FL180 From 210001-220657 Plotted 6-May-1998 14:59

STATIC PRESSURE (MB)

No of obs 4017
 Mean 507.151
 Standard dev 0.125854
 Max value 507.538
 Min value 506.694

DEICED TRUE TEMP (DEG K)

No of obs 4017
 Mean 264.951
 Standard dev 0.594960
 Max value 265.059
 Min value 263.587

DEW POINT (DEG K)

No of obs 4017
 Mean 242.729
 Standard dev 5.26001
 Max value 258.559
 Min value 236.243

OZONE MIXING RATIO (PPB)

No of obs 4017
 Mean 56.6569
 Standard dev 6.61182
 Max value 79.2622
 Min value 45.0721

PSAP LIN ABS COEFF ()

No of obs 4017
 Mean 6.436551e-07
 Standard dev 1.436424e-06
 Max value 1.041522e-05
 Min value -1.046657e-09

JNO2 TOTAL (10-3/S)

No of obs 4017
 Mean 43.9000
 Standard dev 0.000000
 Max value 43.9000
 Min value 43.9000

PRESSURE HEIGHT (METRES)

No of obs 4017
 Mean 5469.50
 Standard dev 1.83562
 Max value 5476.16
 Min value 5463.85

CORRECTED LATITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 4017
 Mean 40.0150
 Standard dev 1.15482
 Max value 41.9569
 Min value 37.9774

CORRECTED LONGITUDE (DEGREES)

No of obs 4017
 Mean -21.2458
 Standard dev 1.47126
 Max value -18.5943
 Min value -23.7142

NORTHWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 4017
 Mean -2.63763
 Standard dev 0.946605
 Max value 0.193657
 Min value -4.99329

EASTWARD WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 4017
 Mean 7.92811
 Standard dev 0.760641
 Max value 10.2184
 Min value 5.92843

VERTICAL WIND COMPT (M S-1)

No of obs 4017
 Mean 0.133665
 Standard dev 0.205576
 Max value 0.896667
 Min value -0.795853

WIND SPEED (MS-1)

No of obs 4017
 Mean 8.40866
 Standard dev 0.762167
 Max value 10.6797
 Min value 6.22416

WIND DIRECTION (DEG)

Mean 288.402

TRUE AIR SPEED (M S-1)

No of obs 4017
 Mean 158.884
 Standard dev 0.399715
 Max value 159.898
 Min value 157.812

HEADING (DEG)

Mean 224.653

4

3

A574 13-SEP-97 P2 FL180 - 3500' From 220657-222156 Plotted 6-May-1998 10:37

A574 13-SEP-97 P2 FL180 - 3500' From 220657-222156 Plotted 6-May-1998 10:37

A574 13-SEP-97 P2 FL180 - 3500' From 220657-222156 Plotted 6-May-1998 10:37

Glossary

Aircraft Position, Speed and Attitude

- **Navigation:** The aircraft carries GPS, OMEGA, and inertial navigation systems.
- **Pressure height:** is based on the standard atmosphere as specified by the International Civil Aviation Organisation (sea level pressure of 1013.25 hPa). Pressure height is quoted in terms of Flight Levels (height in hundreds of feet *e.g.* FL100 = 10000 feet).
- **Radar height:** altitude of the aircraft above surface, measured by radar.
- **Time:** All times are UTC.

General meteorology

- **Tephigrams:** are given for every major profile of each flight. A tephigram is a thermodynamic diagram (temperature (T) - entropy (ϕ) diagram) used to assess the static stability of a given atmospheric profile. Other meteorological organisations use similar diagrams such as the Emagram or the Skew T log p diagram.
- **Deiced true temperature:** air temperature with corrections for aircraft speed and altitude.
- **Potential temperature:** the temperature that a parcel of air would have if it follows a dry adiabatic lapse rate to the 1000 hPa level.
- **Dew point:** dew point (the temperature at which a sample of air would just become saturated with respect to a plane surface of water if cooled at a constant pressure) calculated from the chilled mirror General Eastern hygrometer.

Particle Data

- **CNC:** Condensation nucleus counter (this data is provisional and requires further validation). The measurement is from a commercial instrument: TSI INC Model 3025A. Although CNC data were recorded on the flight no post flight processing has been carried out. Rather than delay this booklet further, I have decided to wait and process the data when the validation has been carried out by the cloud physics group.
- **PSAP:** The Radiance Research Particle Soot Absorption Photometer gives a measurement of optical absorption by black carbon, using a quartz filter with the absorption measured at 565 nm.

Chemistry Parameters

- **Ozone:** Calibrated readings from the TECO 49 ozone analyser in ppb. Instrument scientist: Joss Kent and Ken Dewey (UK Met. Office).
- **JNO₂:** The sum of upward and downward facing radiometers (data not quality controlled). Instrument scientists: Christoph Gerbig and Sandra Schmitgen (FZ Jülich).
- **Hydrogen peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb (approx.). Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Organic peroxide:** Raw data recorded in ppb (approx.). Instrument scientist: Brian Bandy (UEA Norwich).
- **Formaldehyde:** Raw data (approx) converted to ppb using approximate scale factor and offset. Instrument scientist: Graham Mills (UEA, Norwich).
- **NO_x:** Parameters (NO, NO₂, NO_y) were recorded on MRF's data recording system and are plotted in bits. Only one NO_y channel was available for this flight. Instrument scientist: Stephane Bauguitte (UEA, Norwich).
- **Bottles:** Please refer to the bottle flight logs (within the flight folder section) to see when these were filled. Analysis carried out at NILU.
- **CO:** Approximate data in ppb from the DRS. Instrument scientist: Sandra Schmitgen (fz-Jülich).

ARASF

For more information contact:

**Met. Research Flight
Y46 Building, D.E.R.A.
Farnborough, Hants GU14 6TD**

Fax: +44 (0) 1252-376588

**Dr. Andrew Kaye
NERC Scientific Liaison
Tel: +44 (0) 1252-395843
E-mail: A.Kaye@nerc.ac.uk**

**Dr. Hannah Richer
Tel: +44 (0) 1252-395830
E-mail: hricher@meto.gov.uk**

**Mr. Illyea Hawke
Tel: +44 (0) 1252-395840
E-mail: idhawke@meto.gov.uk**

